

Bible and Christianity, the Colonial weapon.

The complexity and yet nuanced historical tales that interlink the Bible and Christianity with Colonialism have unveiled the multidimensional responsibilities that religion took as a tool of control and power. The Bible, a holy book that became not only a spiritual guide as European authorities went abroad on colonial endeavors, but adapted and wielded into a powerful religious weapon towards legitimizing and propagating imperialist activities. In a disturbing connection, Missionaries, the heralds of faith, were crucial for the pivotal roles of disseminating Christian guidelines besides colonial dominance.

The Biblical verses were keenly selected and interpreted to justify suppression, cultural assimilation, and colonization. To provide a brief review of the Bible's history and introduction, Christianity, and colonization, let us begin in precolonial times. Long before contemporary European conquest occurred, the Bible was predominantly brought to Asia and Africa via sea routes heavily laden with economic products. And because the Bible was regarded as the treasure of the Gospel, only travelers, monks, and traders were permitted to transport it (Punt, Porter, & Stanley, 2008). As a result, this study will focus on two accounts: the Bible, Christianity, and Colonialism in Europe, Africa, and Asia.

Bible and Colonialism in Europe

Throughout history, colonialism has been characterized as a sort of imperialism in which an imperial state establishes governmental control over an area without considerable human settlement (Harvey, 2016). As a result, since colonialism entails colonizing a region or administering it from a distance, it is reasonable to argue that colonialism is just a manifestation

of imperialism. Harvey disputed that the meaning evolved when Europeans arrived on new continents and began bringing local governments under the sway of their crowns. As a consequence, the earliest known imperial structures were quite traditional, akin to the Ottoman, Roman, and modern Spanish and Portuguese models of imperialism. This was an imperial strategy based on bureaucracy with pre-capitalist principles. It took the form of a military invasion to capture territory, plunder wealth, levy direct taxes, and convert the native population to the conqueror's religion (Nygard, 2017).

Moreover, Young (1998) underlined that, while British imperial philosophy promoted reliance and control, French imperial thought was primarily about colonization and conquest. This was the primary distinction between the two countries he compared, France and Britain. Young argues that French imperialism was motivated by nationalism, the desire to safeguard internal political stability, and France's welfare. The desire for France's glory was similar, particularly in terms of repairing its prestige on the European continent during the great Napoleonic Empire. Motivated by this aim, France abandoned Europe and set out to subjugate the world. Daughton (2006), underscores that France's massive colonization efforts were accompanied by the integration of its religious and cultural traditions at the expense of the population's faith and way of life.

Furthermore, it is established that the growth of Christianity was closely related to Western imperialism, to bring European culture to less civilized nations, including Christianization and education of the non-Western globe. According to (Robert, 2009), the Bible's translation helped Catholic missions regain their strength and spread during the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries as they worked to heal from the immense harm the Reformation had inflicted. The goal of Catholic

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missionaries from various missions, particularly Jesuits, is to spread the gospel throughout the world. Catholic missionaries collaborated with the Spanish and Portuguese colonial rulers during the invasions of Latin America to convert the native population to Catholicism. Robert writes that "the majority of Catholic missions from the sixteenth to the eighteenth centuries coexisted with the colonial expansion of Catholic countries in the Americas and Southeast Asia," highlighting the collaboration amongst the colonizers and the Catholic missions generally.

Besides, in biblical history, the invasion of Canaan prepared the way for the conquest of Europe. The war against the native people is justified by the biblical story of the Canaanites' conquest. The conquest is explained away as a special gift from God, akin to the Promised Land, rather than as retribution for blasphemy. God gives the Spaniards the ability to conquer the infidels' lands and execute divine justice against them. According to Medina (2019), when it came to the mission of Joshua, it was well known that, as a result of idolatry and crimes, God had sentenced the people of Abya Yala to death and to suffer from illnesses and epidemics. The Bible contained the responses to each of these questions. God sent Joshua, his servant, to wipe out seven generations of idolaters and bring the sons of Israel into the land (Joshua 18:3). It has been established that Joshua's scriptural explanation is reduced to the declaration, "It is in the Bible, and that is what should be."

In addition, the debate about imperialism continued from the Middle Ages until the present. This is recent, from 1989 when Panama was invaded. Similarly, in 1991, an alliance of democratic Europeans and Americans invaded the Persian Gulf to liberate it. These two instances made it quite clear that suffering is either God's will or His punishment. Biblical theology, which is popular in many of our churches, obscures the mechanisms underlying the suffering. So, we can all agree, at

least in part, that Christianity is frequently associated with exploitation, brutality, and tribute. The Bible takes a negative position toward indigenous peoples because they see the Christian canon as an enemy to their survival. Since the Bible was a vital weapon in dominance, Indigenous peoples' expressions, and awful experiences are primarily related to exploration and colonization. Tragically, the pain never ends because the Bible's fundamental teachings are repeatedly used to enslave Indigenous religions.

Bible, Christianity and Colonialism in Africa.

Trade provided the first point of interaction between European countries, represented by Portugal, and Africa's western coast in the fifteenth century. Following unsuccessful initiatives to delve into the continent's interior, European nations focused their trade and mission efforts on Africa's mineral-rich coastlines. The history of modern imperialism, on the other hand, begins with Livingstone's expedition of the continent to popularize Christianity, Western civilization, and trade, as well as his plea to Britain in 1857 to allow British trade to reach Africa's heartland (Darwin, 2009). Cox denotes that, Christian missionaries played an important role in the European invasion at this time since they attended the gathering and pretended to endorse their sponsors' ideological objective (Cox, 2007).

Moreover, Christian nations frequently used the Bible as a foundation for cross-referencing colonialism, particularly about ideas regarding particular people and land acquisition. Darwin demonstrates how Protestant regimes' desire for power and their economic greed drove the expansion of Western imperialism, which was motivated in large part by the hunger for Bibles and territory. In addition, colonialists devised a three-pronged devious defense to assert their entitlement to the lands of the settlers: the claim of being conquerors, the claim of appropriating

lands populated by absentee herders or hunter-gatherers, and the claim of bringing the aboriginal people under civilized control. Indeed, the moral issues are presented in the book of Deuteronomy, which could be interpreted as containing colonialism and conveying the perception that humanity is to be annexed as if it has already been given over by The LORD to His faithful. The verse reads, "You shall devour all the people that Yahweh your God is giving over to you, showing them no pity" (Deuteronomy 7:16).

Additionally, during the pre-colonial era, in Asia and Africa, the Bible was considered a sectional manuscript since its writings were only based on foreign languages and lacked interpretation of the local language for the inhabitants. Besides, the holy book suffered a scarcity of duplicates, making it unfamiliar. The case is similar in the European's lives where the Bible did not hold any position in the life of individual believers during the pre-Reformation era. Thereafter, the Bible was seen as very crucial at times when the colonial was embryonic. The Bible was made easily accessible to individuals via the Biblical – civilizations to spread the scriptures to the colonies. The action of disseminating Biblical writings and their translation proliferated the European culture, notwithstanding its contributions to the discovery of knowledge and truth (Maluleke, 2002).

Furthermore, the Biblical interpretation by the missionaries during the colonial embrace was intended to sustain the status quo. Christian missionaries played a critical role and they were wholesomely responsible for the loss of lands and misery deeds, the eroding of cultures, and the whole shebang that Africans could see as their valuable asset triggered by their cooperation with the colonists. The arguments were advanced and the results propagated the Gospel which eventually preceded the arrival of the Europeans who came and arrogated the lands of the

indigenes. The Bible gained traction in the fight for African land because it was used to justify European imperialism. Because Africans saw only a God who supported injustice, the abolition of their customs, and the loss of their territory, the missionaries' attitude misrepresented the Christian God. This viewpoint is reflected in the old African adage, which asserts that white people had the Bible and black people had the lands, but after the missionaries prayed, white people had the lands and black people had the Bible (Marandi, & Shadpour, 2011).

In conclusion, the above study demonstrates how Christian missions and colonial rule concurred during the colonial period: rulers were willing to use force if necessary to propagate Christianity around the world, and they considered their secular undertakings as religious endeavors as well. With the Bible in their grasp at the expense of their lives, lands, and traditions, the colonial race resulted in Africans losing more than they gained during the colonial missions. The colonies' general disrespect for indigenous typifies contemporary African imperialism motivated by religious belief. Similar to how European powers just copied what biblical Israel did to countries they deemed unbelievers for having a sense of racial along with religious supremacy derived from their Bible, Europeans, and Asians were also subjected to colonialism.

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